

DEEPICE

Research and training network on understanding Deep ice core Proxies to Infer past antarctic climate dynamics

H2020-MSCA-ITN-2020 – ETN European Training Networks

Deliverable 2.1: Report on field season measurement and instrumentation protocol

Deliverable number: 2.1

Due date: M12 (December 2021)

Nature: Report

Dissemination Level: Public

Work Package: WP 2 – Quantification of processes responsible for creation and alteration of the climate signal in the ice core

Lead Beneficiary of the deliverable: CNRS

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 955750

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Document history

Version	Date	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Notes
1.0	04/05/2021	Marie Kazeroni	Amaëlle Landais	
1.1	10/05/2021	Marie Kazeroni	Amaëlle Landais	

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Abbreviations

DDU: Dumont d'Urville

ESR: Early Stage Researcher

LDC: Little Dome C

IPEV: French Polar Institute Paul-Emile Victor

LSCE: Laboratory for Sciences of Climate and Environment

Table of content

Summary	6
1. Context of the field missions	7
1.1. Context for ESR 10 project	7
1.2. Context for ESR 11 project	8
2. Protocols for instrumentation.....	9
2.1. Protocol for the measurements of isotopic composition of water vapour, precipitation, surface snow and sub-surface snow on the East Antarctic plateau.....	9
2.2. Protocol for the firn air pumping campaigns	10
3. Materials to be imported / exported from the EU.....	11
4. Measures to minimize the impact on the environment	12
Annexes	13
Annex 1 – Protocol for instrumentation of ICORDA-KATABIC project	13
Annex 2 - Protocol for instrumentation of NIVO project	19
Annex 3 – List of the material imported from EU to Antarctica	25

Summary

The deliverable presents the context of the field missions in Antarctica linked with DEEPICE ESR 10 and ESR 11 projects.

It contains the protocols for instrumentation related to the field missions, as well as an explanation on the material that will be imported and exported.

It also includes the measures that will be implemented to minimize the impact of the field missions on the environment.

1. Context of the field missions

There are two PhD projects involved in field missions in Antarctica within DEEPICE:

- PhD project of ESR 10: interpretation of the water isotope climate signal on the east Antarctic plateau through continuous measurements of isotopic composition of water vapour, precipitation, surface snow and sub-surface snow
- PhD project of ESR 11: evolution of snow and air circulating in snow beyond the surface of Antarctic ice sheet

These field missions are connected with other projects.

Regarding the field mission related to continuous measurements of isotopic composition of water vapour, precipitation, surface snow and sub-surface snow (ESR 10), this campaign is also associated with the [IPEV-NIVO](#) project and the ERC project [ICORDA](#) and the ANR project [KATABATIC](#).

Regarding the field mission related to the firn air pumping campaign for analyses of air isotopic and elemental composition (ESR 11), this campaign is associated with the ERC project [ICORDA](#) and the ANR project [KATABATIC](#).

1.1. Context for ESR 10 project

The project includes field measurements in Antarctica to study the evolution of the isotopic composition over the whole year (summer and winter seasons) at Concordia.

The interest for measuring and analyzing water isotopes is primarily driven by the study of post depositional processes that affect snow when it is near the surface under the influence of the atmosphere, but this interest is obviously aimed at the interpretation of ice cores for past climate study, such as the future Beyond EPICA ice core.

The field work will consist in the installation of material for measuring the isotopic composition of the snow and vapor in the air for a period of 4 years.

More precisely, the material installed will be:

- a Picarro isotope analyzer, which was removed in 2020 as it was defective and which will be reinstalled
- a low humidity SARA H2O for measurements of isotopic composition of water vapor

These instruments will be installed in 2021 at Concordia.

An important objective here related to the Beyond EPICA project (with consists in a deep drilling at Little Dome C (LDC), 40 km from Concordia) is to compare the isotopic composition at the surface (water vapor - precipitation - surface snow) at LDC and at Concordia during a summer season. This is essential to interpret the future water isotopic record of the Beyond EPICA ice core.

The comparison of the two sites will be the subject of ESR 10 project.

Thus, in addition to the 2 instruments installed at Concordia, a PICARRO or SARA-H2O instrument to measure water vapor isotopic composition will be installed at LDC for 3 weeks during the field season

2022-2023 (it was initially planned for 2021-2022 field season but because of the COVID-19 crisis, this has been delayed). In addition to the water vapor analyzer, a weather station will be installed as well as a system for measurements of water vapor exchange fluxes at the snow – atmosphere interface.

1.2. Context for ESR 11 project

Within ESR 11 project, firn air will be pumped for analyses of air isotopic and elemental composition in the open porosity in order to better understand and characterize thermal effect and close-off processes on the elemental and isotopic composition of the air.

2 major campaigns are associated with ESR 11 and they will consist of:

- a firn air pumping system will be installed in austral summer 2021-2022 for a whole year at Concordia where air will be pumped on the top 20 m of the firn. Firn air will be pumped for analyses of air isotopic and elemental (nitrogen, oxygen, noble gases) composition in the open porosity over 6 different depth levels (depths of 3, 6, 9, 12, 15 and 18 m). 4 samples per hole will be collected every 3 months during the whole year. 2 drillings will be realized to do so, each of them will be equipped with 3 tubes at different depth level to pump the air in the firn.
- two firn air campaigns at D47 and LDC, where two 120m-drillings will be realised during the season 2022-2023.

The map below indicates the different sites where the measurements will take place.

Figure 1: Location of the different sites mentioned (DC = Concordia ; DDU= Dumont D'Urville ; LDC=Little Dome C). The sites indicated in black are the sites where a firn air campaign will take place. The sites indicated in red are already equipped by a laser spectroscopy instrument and continuous measurements of water isotopic composition are currently performed (since November 2018).

2. Protocols for instrumentation

The whole protocols submitted to IPEV are attached as annexes of this deliverable (see [Annex 1](#) and [Annex 2](#))

2.1. Protocol for the measurements of isotopic composition of water vapour, precipitation, surface snow and sub-surface snow on the East Antarctic plateau

- Austral summer 2021-2022 (December-January most likely) at Concordia

The detailed steps for isotopic measurements are:

- Installation of the defective Picarro isotope analyzer removed last year in the snow shelter
 - Installation of the low humidity SARA-H₂O isotopic analyzer in the snow shelter¹
 - Restarting the calibration of SARA-H₂O instrument
 - Intensive calibration of the two isotopic analyzers
 - Bi-weekly sampling for water isotopic composition of surface snow
- Winter 2022 (February to November 2022) at Concordia

A winterover (person who spend the winter season in Antarctica) will carry out:

- Bi-weekly measurements snow isotope sampling
- Weekly checks of the level of water standard and pressure of the dry air B50 bottle for the calibration instrument in the snow shelter
- Replacement of water standard and dry air B50 bottle every 4 months on the calibration instrument
- Keep contact with LSCE researcher/engineer who is in charge of the daily check of the instrument - maintenance operations can be requested.

- Austral summer 2022-2023 at LDC

In parallel to the drilling and air pumping measurements (ESR 11 project) at LDC:

- Implementation of an instrument for continuous measurement of water vapor isotopic composition at LDC (PICARRO or SARA-H₂O)
- Installation of a weather station on the scientific trailer that will be used during the campaign as well as a system for measurements of water vapor exchange fluxes at the snow – atmosphere interface at LDC
- Installation of a mast to pump water vapor at 3 m height above the surface and a PFA tube heated at about 30°C to avoid condensation.
- Daily water vapor isotopic measurements.
- Daily sampling of surface snow samples for further water isotopic analyses in the laboratory.

¹ This still has to be confirmed as because of the COVID19 crisis, some field words have to be adjusted.

2.2. Protocol for the firn air pumping campaigns

Firn air pumping campaign at Concordia:

- November - December 2021:
 - Drilling and installation of the firn air pumping experiment at Concordia. First sampling.
- The detailed steps are:
- Realization of the two 20m-drillings with short hand drill (FOR-POSSUM core drill) at 80 m from the "Atmos" shelter
 - Installation of the firn air pumping system: 3 dekabon tubes per drilling will be installed at different depth levels (3 m, 6 m, 9 m, 12m, 15 m and 18 m) with a central cable. These tubes must be linked by a cable tray to the "Atmos" shelter
 - Filling the holes with 400micron inert glass microbeads
 - Installation of a pumping system in the pump room of the "Atmos" shelter
 - Leak testing of the system using SARA-CH4 and CO instruments
 - First firn air sampling at the 6 depth levels and check of the whole procedure
 - Training of the overwinterer on the firn air pumping system and sampling
- March 2022, June 2022, September 2022:
 - Second, third and fourth sampling of surface firn air at Concordia
 - June 2022:
 - Reception of the samples in the different institutes for analyses
 - Beginning of analytical work on the different samples
 - Reception of laser analyser in the lab and calibration
 - December 2022:
 - Uninstallation of surface firn air sampling at Concordia (3 days maximum)

Firn air pumping campaign at LDC and D47

- November 2022 – February 2023:
 - Transect between Cap Prud'homme and Little Dome C with 3-4 weeks camp at D47 and 3-4 weeks camp at LDC

For each sampling operation at D47 and LDC, at least 4 persons (1 logistic, 1 driller and 2 scientists) and one drilling system should be allocated for each sampling operation.

A scientific trailer will be used during for the two campaigns.

The following field operations are foreseen:

- 3-4 days at DDU: calibration of the laser analyser and preparation of the traverse
- 1 day transportation from Cad Prud'homme to D47
- 4 weeks at D47:
 - Installation of the camp
 - Installation of a wind protected area to perform the drilling and firn air pumping
 - Drilling and firn air pumping (3 weeks)

- End of operations and packing
- 10 days transportation to LDC
- 3-4 weeks at LDC:
 - Installation of the camp
 - Drilling and firn air pumping (3 weeks)
 - End of operations and packing
- 1 day transportation to Concordia
- 2 days at Concordia: calibration of the laser analyser

3. Materials to be imported / exported from the EU

The list of materials that will be exported from the EU to Antarctica is detailed in [Annex 3](#) of this deliverable.

The materials that will be imported from Antarctica to the EU are:

- air samples (contained in canisters)
- frozen and melted ice samples

Figure 1: example of material sent to Antarctica for the firn air pumping campaign

Figure 2: Boxes for the transportation of the material for the campaigns

4. Measures to minimize the impact on the environment

The drillings foreseen for the firm airn pumping campaigns will consist in dry drillings, in opposition to deep ice core drillings which use polluting drilling fluids so that pollution is avoided.

Regarding the two 20m-drillings that will be performed at Concordia, it was initially planned to import sand and use it to fill the holes. In order to avoid the import of natural material in Antarctica, alternative solutions have been researched. In the end, sand will be replaced by glass microbeads. As glass is an inert material and doesn't contain germs, it is a better solution to minimize the impact of the environment. The microbeads will have to be installed for a minimum of one year in order to pump the air in the firm. Once the campaign is finished, the microbeads can be removed if necessary with a vacuum system, and the tubes installed in the holes could also be removed. This could be done during the summer 2022-2023 field season.

Regarding the two 120m-drillings that will be realized at D47 and LDC during the firm airn campaigns in summer 2022-2023, these drillings will also consist in dry drillings and won't be filled with any material. After the 3 weeks of campaign at each site, the whole installation is removed, so nothing is left on site.

Another important issue to consider with respect to the Antarctic treaty environment protocol is the waste management. The field operations mentioned above will take place at both Concordia and Little Dome C where scientific stations already exist. Waste there will be mainly composed of food, human and domestic wastes. Potential impacts will be handled following Concordia System policies and procedures currently in place, such as waste management protocols for separating, containing, and returning wastes from field camps. At Little Dome C, the wastes, except for sewage will be collected and taken back to Concordia Station and then away from the Antarctic Treaty Area.

Regarding the campaign at D47, the waste produced can easily be transported by tractor to Cap Prud'homme (distance of 150 km), which is an annex base of the French base Dumont d'Urville where there are also procedures in place to handle waste.

Annexes

Annex 1 – Protocol for instrumentation of ICORDA-KATABIC project

Protocoles de mise en œuvre des opérations scientifiques 2021/2022

<https://sciences.ipev.fr/protocoles/index.php?action=document&zd=642>

1250 ICORDA-KATABATIC Antarctico Other

Eté

Protocoles de mise en œuvre des opérations scientifiques 2021/2022

1 - Personnel

Personne	Statut	Vers district	Retour district	Commentaire
Roxanne Jacob ♀ Org : CNRS roxanne.jacob@lsce.ipsl.fr	Collaborateur National	HBT- MZS (DC)	R2 in	Roxanne Jacob est la personne à envoyer en priorité pour le LSCE pour les programmes ICORDA-KATABATIC, ADELISE et NIVO (s'il ne devait y en avoir qu'une) // Dans le statut, il s'agit de personnel de laboratoire (ingénieur)
Grégory Teste ♂ Org : gregory.teste@univ-grenoble-alpes.fr	Personnel de laboratoire			

2 - Objectif scientifique

L'objectif scientifique principal est de mieux contraindre la diffusion de l'air dans le névé et les conditions de piégeage de l'air dans la glace notamment l'influence de ces processus sur la composition élémentaire et isotopique des gaz tels que dioxygène, diazote, argon et autres gaz rares. Pour l'année 2021, l'objectif est d'installer un système pour pomper l'air des 20 premiers mètres du névé à plusieurs reprises pendant

toute une année (incluant un pompage l'hiver). Cette étude est le coeur d'une thèse du projet européen ITN DEEPICE et de l'ERC ICORDA.

3 - Opération

A terre :

Les opérations décrites sont les opérations minimales (impossible de faire moins)

Eté (Concordia):

- Réalisation de 2 forages de 20 m avec le carottier FOR-POSSUM à 80 m du shelter "Atmos" (endroit précédemment balisé par l'hivernante glacio) (2 jours, 2 personnes)
- Installation d'un système de pompage: 3 tubes en dékabon par trou de forage avec un câble central lesté, ces tubes doivent être reliés par un chemin de câbles jusqu'au shelter "Atmos" (2 jours, 2 personnes)
- Remplissage des trous avec des microbilles de verre inerte de 400 microns (2 jours, 2 personnes)
- Installation d'un système de pompage dans la salle des pompes du shelter "Atmos" (2 jours, 1 personne)
- Test de l'étanchéité du système en utilisant le SARA-CH4 et CO (2 jours, 1 personne)
- Premier pompage des 6 niveaux de profondeur et formation de l'hivernant sur cette manipulation à faire pendant l'hiver (3 jours, 1 personne + hivernant)
- Test du matériel de pompage d'air pour la campagne 2022-2023 (à faire en parallèle pendant 15 jours dans le tubosider, besoin de 2 personnes 1 journée pour installation au début)

Eté (LDC):

- Test du carottier 300 m sur un forage de 100 m (1 personne, 15 jours en parallèle aux opérations de Beyond EPICA)

A bord ou à partir des navires :

4 - Logistique sur base

4a - Bâtiment

Nom	Instrument	Durée (j)	Période	Commentaire
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2 forages de 20 m à 80 m du shelter "atmos" carottier forpossum 2 début de saison 2021-2022 Les 2 forages resteront en place pendant 1 an

4b - Laboratoire

Type	Surface (m ²)	Durée (j)	Période	Commentaire
Système de pompage dans le shelter ATMOS (salle des pompes)	2	365	installation en été	

4c - Bureau

4d - Stockage

Type de matériel	Dimension	Température	Durée (j)	Période	Commentaire
caisse avec 30 silcocans	120*80*80	Hors gel	365	toute l'année	

4e - Données

Type	Volume (Mo)	Fréquence	Direction	Besoins spécifiques
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4f - Commentaire

Besoin d'installer un chemin de câble pour le chemin des tuyaux en dékaton entre les trous de forage et le shelter "atmos". Installer un passe-cloison dans le shelter "atmos".

5 - Logistique hors base

5a - Logistique

Durée : 0 jour(s)	Période :	Nb personne : 0	Nb soutien : 0
Besoins dédiés :		Objectifs :	
Moyens d'accès :		Commentaire :	

5b - Commentaire

6 - Transport

6a - Transport de matériel (hors dangereux)

Direction	Rotation	Temp (°C)	Nb	Poids (kg)	Volume (m ³)	Commentaire
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	1	100	200*30*30	Carottier FOR POSSUM
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	29	25	30*20*60	sacs de microbilles de verre à 400 microns
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	2	30	120*80*80	caisses avec Silcocans (à stocker en hors gel quand elles auront été remplies)
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	2	100	100*100*50	Enrouleurs avec dekabon 1/4 pouce
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	1	25	80*80*60	Pompe suisse
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	1	25	80*80*60	Table de pompage avec système de vannes et jauges

Vers la base	R0 in	Hors gel	1	30	100*40*80	SARA-CH4 et CO
Vers la base	R0 in	Hors gel	1	25	60*40*40	Grosse pompe SARA-CH4; matériel calibration et connexion SARA CH4-CO outillage
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	1	30	80*60*60	Matériel pour pompage air névé (raccords, filtres, vannes et jauges de secours, outils, câble)
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	1	300	500*100*100	Carottier 300m
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	2	30	300*40*40	manchons et brides pour pompage air névé
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	1	30	80*60*60	Matériel pour test pompage air névé dans tubosider (pompe, outillage, raccords)
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	1	200	200*200*100	Enrouleur 3*130 m tube de kabon en 3/8 pour campagne 2022-2023
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	2	30	120*80*80	canisters silcocans pour campagne 2022-2023
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	1	100	200*200*100	tente forage
Vers la base	R2 in	Hors gel	1	30	80*60*60	LICOR
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	1	30	80*60*60	Matériel découpe et pompage air autour échantillons prélevés
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	1	20	60*40*40	Gaine pour stockage carottes de glace
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	1	40	80*60*60	Récipients pour échantillons porosité ouverte près du close-off; petit outillage pour fermer ces récipients; petit matériel pour loggin des carottes
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	1	25	80*60*60	Table avec vannes et jauges pour pompage sur la campagne ICORDA-KATABATIC

Vers la base R2 in Hors gel 1 25 80*60*60 Pompes de recharge, petit matériel pour campagne ICORDA - KATABATIC

6b - Transport de produits dangereux

6c - Commentaire

7 - Chronogramme

Été (Concordia):

- Réalisation de 2 forages de 20 m avec le carottier FOR-POSSUM à 80 m du shelter "Atmos" (endroit précédemment balisé par l'hivernante glacio) (2 jours, 2 personnes)
- Installation d'un système de pompage: 3 tubes en dékabon par trou de forage avec un câble central lesté, ces tubes doivent être reliés par un chemin de câbles jusqu'au shelter "Atmos" (2 jours, 2 personnes)
- Remplissage des trous avec des microbilles de verre inerte de 400 microns (2 jours, 2 personnes)
- Installation d'un système de pompage dans la salle des pompes du shelter "Atmos" (2 jours, 1 personne)
- Test de l'étanchéité du système en utilisant le SARA-CH4 et CO (2 jours, 1 personne)
- Premier pompage des 6 niveaux de profondeur et formation de l'hivernant sur cette manipulation à faire pendant l'hiver (3 jours, 1 personne + hivernant)
- Test du matériel de pompage d'air pour la campagne 2022-2023 (à faire en parallèle pendant 15 jours dans le tubosider, besoin de 2 personnes 1 journée pour installation au début)

Été (LDC):

- Test du carottier 300 m sur un forage de 100 m (1 personne, 15 jours en parallèle aux opérations de Beyond EPICA)

Institut polaire français

Annex 2 - Protocol for instrumentation of NIVO project

Protocols for implementation of scientific operations 2021/2022

<https://sciences.ipev.fr/protocoles/index.php?action=document&zid=570>1110 NIVO Antarctica Concordia

Summer

Protocols for implementation of scientific operations 2021/2022

1 - Staff

Staff	Status	To district	From district	Comment
Laurent Arnaud	Laboratory staff	HBT-MZS (DDU)	HBT-MZS (DC)	
Org : CNRS laurent.arnaud@univ-grenoble- alpes.fr	Engineer or technician			

2 - Scientific objective

The program aims at monitoring the snow changes. It consists in 1) measurements of the snow physical properties, mainly using automatic instruments at and around Dome C, and 2) measurements of the isotopic composition of the snow and vapor in the air.

3 - Field operations

Two main activities will be conducted during the next summer season:

- 1) The snow physics (Snow-WP) will be carried out by Laurent Arnaud mainly.
- 2) The isotopic measurements (Iso-WP) at Dome C will be carried out by Amélie Landais from the Adélise project or Roxanne Jacob from the ICORDA-KATABATIC person if only one person from LSCE is

allowed to go to the field.

Snow-WP: in collaboration with Eric Lefebvre if possible.

- servicing the snow instruments in the NIVO park: The laserscanner RLS needs some important repair. The other instruments only need minor checks (at time of writing).

- dismantling the stations at 25km South and North. This needs to be done soon or later, these stations do not work optimally anymore.

Iso-WP:

- Installation of the defective Picarro isotope analyzer removed last year in the snow shelter -> This operation must be done this year (2 days)

- Installation of the SARA-H2O isotopic analyzer in the snow shelter (5 days) -> If we have to reduce the season and send only one person from LSCE, we remove this step.

- Restarting the calibration instrument -> This operation must be done this summer (5 days)

- Intensive calibration of the two isotopic analyzers (10 days) -> If we have to reduce the season and send only one person, the calibration of the only instrument will be done by the winterover with remote assistance

4 - Logistical on base

4a - Instrument

Laserscan (RLS)	Size: 40x40x40	Weight: 10 kg	Running temp: -80°C	
Other:				
Power	<u>Average</u> 0.3kW	<u>Peak</u> 0.3kW	<u>Annex</u> kW	
Location	<u>main</u> Outside	<u>Height</u> 10m	<u>Distance</u> m	
	<u>Annex</u>	<u>Horizontal field of view</u>	<u>Vertical field of view</u>	
Operational	<u>Mode</u> Automatic	<u>Monitoring frequency</u> daily	<u>Control</u>	
Comment :				

laser spectroscopy instrument	Size:	Weight: 30 kg		Running temp: Off-frost
		50*50*25		
	Other:			
	Power	<u>Average</u> 0.2kW	<u>Peak</u> 0.2kW	<u>Annex</u> 0.1kW
	Location	<u>main</u> Inside	<u>Height</u> 0.8m	<u>Distance</u> m
	<u>Annex</u> Close to the instrument	<u>Horizontal field of view</u>	<u>Vertical field of view</u>	
Operational	<u>Mode</u>	<u>Monitoring frequency</u> Continuously	<u>Control</u> Local control on instrument location	
Comment : This instrument has been removed for repair and will be back in the snow shelter at its initial place				

Laser spectroscopy instrument	Size:	Weight: 30 kg		Running temp: Off-frost
		50*50*25		
	Other:			
	Power	<u>Average</u> 0.2kW	<u>Peak</u> 0.2kW	<u>Annex</u> 0.1kW
	Location	<u>main</u> Inside	<u>Height</u> 0.8m	<u>Distance</u> m
	<u>Annex</u> Close to the instrument	<u>Horizontal field of view</u>	<u>Vertical field of view</u>	
Operational	<u>Mode</u> Automatic	<u>Monitoring frequency</u> continuously	<u>Control</u> Remote control from the station	
Comment : New instrument (SARA-H2O) already deployed in 2019-2020 in the snow shelter with the other instrument				

4b - Preparation

Surface (m ²)	Heating	Duration (d)	Period	Comment
2	Yes	15	summer	Preparation / repair of the instruments in the Epica workshop

4c - Storage

Type	Size	Temp	Weight (kg)	Duration (d)	Period	Comment
Laserscan (RLS) spare and tools	1m2	Ambiant	Ambiant	15	Summer	In the EPIC workshop
Samples for isotopes	1 box	-20°C	-20°C	365	Winter	box to be filled during the year
Empty cornings	80*60*60	Ambiant	Ambiant	365	Winter	

4d - Data

Type	Volume (MB)	Frequency	Direction	Specific needs
data	100	daily	From base	Isotopes data and snow data
control of the instruments	5	occasional	To base	To control the instruments

4e - Comment

5 - On site

5a - Technical support

Skill	Period	Comment
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5b - Technical means

Mean	Period	Frequency	Use time (h)	Distance from station (m)	Comment
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PB100 summer Twice 8 25000 Visit of the 25km Nord and South

5c - Comment

Visit of the 25km South and North sites

6 - Transport

6a - Material transport (except dangerous goods)

Direction	Rotation	Temp (°C)	Nb	Weight (kg)	Volume (m³)	Comment
To base	HBT-MZS (DC)	Ambiant	1	50	80X60X60	RLS maintenance
From base	R4 out	Ambiant	2	50	80X60x60	return of the 2 stations at 25 km
To base	HBT-MZS (DC)	Off-frost	3	150	80x60x60	3 boxes with: - Picarro laser spectroscopy instrument - SARA-H2O - Pumps for the two instrument, computer, connection, tubes, standards
To base	R2 in	Ambiant	1	30	50x40x40	- 200 cornings can be R2 ou R3.
From base	R4 out	-20°C	1	25	80*60*60	Collected samples (in cornings)

6b - Dangerous goods

6c - Comment

7 - Timetable

The Snow activities requires 10 to 15 days:

Staff in charge of snow physics (L. Arnaud): Arrival at DMC from PRUD mid January and departure early February.

- Dismounting RLS (1 day), repair (few days), tests (few days), mounting (1 day), checks ...
- Visit of the other instruments (1 day)
- Training of the winterover staf (1 day)
- Journey at 25km South and North (2 days + organisation)

The isotopes activities require 3 weeks but can be reduced to one week if only one person is sent to the field to adapt to the sanitary situation:

- Installation of the defective Picarro isotope analyzer removed last year in the snow shelter -> This operation must be done this year (2 days)
- Installation of the SARA-H2O isotopic analyzer in the snow shelter (5 days) -> If we have to reduce the season and send only one person from LSCE, we remove this step.
- Restarting the calibration instrument -> This operation must be done this summer (5 days)
- Intensive calibration of the two isotopic analyzers (10 days) -> If we have to reduce the season and send only one person, the calibration of the only instrument will be done by the winterover with remote assistance

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Annex 3 – List of the material imported from EU to Antarctica

Material imported within the ICORDA-KATABATIC project

Direction	Rotation	Temp (°C)	Nb	Poids (kg)	Volume (m³)	Commentaire
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	1	100	200*30*30	Carottier FOR POSSUM
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	29	25	30*20*60	sacs de microbilles de verre à 400 microns
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	2	30	120*80*80	caisses avec Silcocans (à stocker en hors gel quand elles auront été remplies)
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	2	100	100*100*50	Enrouleurs avec dekabon 1/4 pouce
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	1	25	80*80*60	Pompe suisse
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	1	25	80*80*60	Table de pompage avec système de vannes et jauges
Vers la base	R0 in	Hors gel	1	30	100*40*80	SARA-CH4 et CO
Vers la base	R0 in	Hors gel	1	25	60*40*40	Grosse pompe SARA-CH4; matériel calibration et connexion SARA CH4-CO outillage
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	1	30	80*60*60	Matériel pour pompage air névé (raccords, filtres, vannes et jauges de secours, outils, câble)
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	1	300	500*100*100	Carottier 300m
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	2	30	300*40*40	manchons et brides pour pompage air névé
Vers la base	R0 in	Ambiante	1	30	80*60*60	Matériel pour test pompage air névé dans tubosider (pompe, outillage, raccords)
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	1	200	200*200*100	Enrouleur 3*130 m tube dekabon en 3/8 pour campagne 2022-2023
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	2	30	120*80*80	canisters silcocans pour campagne 2022-2023

Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	1	100	200*200*100	tente forage
Vers la base	R2 in	Hors gel	1	30	80*60*60	LICOR
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	1	30	80*60*60	Matériel découpe et pompage air autour échantillons prélevés
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	1	20	60*40*40	Gaine pour stockage carottes de glace
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	1	40	80*60*60	Récipients pour échantillons porosité ouverte près du close-off; petit outillage pour fermer ces récipients; petit matériel pour loggin des carottes
Vers la base	R2 in	Ambiante	1	25	80*60*60	Table avec vannes et jauges pour pompage sur la campagne ICORDA-KATABATIC
Vers la base	R2 in	Hors gel	1	25	80*60*60	Pompes de rechange, petit matériel pour campagne ICORDA - KATABATIC

Material imported within the NIVO project

Direction	Rotation	Temp (°C)	Nb	Weight (kg)	Volume (m³)	Comment
To base	HBT-MZS (DC)	Ambiant	1	50	80X60X60	RLS maintenance
From base	R4 out	Ambiant	2	50	80X60x60	return of the 2 stations at 25 km
To base	HBT-MZS (DC)	Off-frost	3	150	80x60x60	3 boxes with: - Picarro laser spectroscopy instrument - SARA-H2O - Pumps for the two instrument, computer, connection, tubes, standards
To base	R2 in	Ambiant	1	30	50x40x40	- 200 corings can be R2 ou R3.
From base	R4 out	-20°C	1	25	80*60*60	Collected samples (in corings)